

Radicals in Enzymatic Reactions: To B₁₂ or Not To B₁₂?^{1,2}

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General Background

The investigation of radical intermediates in enzymatic catalysis is a subject of growing importance. Nature uses radical reactions because difficult substrates can be easily functionalised, with the result that unusual or surprising reactions are catalysed. The advantages of using radicals as intermediates are their high reactivity and special properties, such as the ability to cleave non-activated C-H bonds. However, this reactivity includes rapid bimolecular combination with dioxygen and radicals are therefore commonly utilised as intermediates by anaerobic rather than aerobic organisms. Examples of reactions in enzymology for which radicals are implicated as intermediates are: coenzyme B₁₂-dependent enzymatic reactions; ribonucleotide reductases (e.g. the enzymes from humans and *Escherichia coli*); 2-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratases; isopenicillin synthase; benzylsuccinate synthase; α -lysine 2,3-aminomutase; pyruvate formate lyase; chorismate synthase [1]. Some of these enzymes utilise neutral radicals as intermediates: for example, those that are coenzyme B₁₂-dependent and perform carbon skeleton rearrangements (e.g. glutamate mutase). Other enzymes may utilise intermediate radical anions (e.g. 2-hydroxyglutaryl-CoA dehydratase).

This paper is focussed on the carbon-skeleton rearrangements catalysed by enzymes that are dependent on coenzyme B₁₂ as cofactor. New approaches to comprehending their mechanisms are described. Although the elucidation of an enzyme's structure was once considered to supersede model studies, it is now clear that the crystal structure analysis of a protein can be utilised in the design of better models. Ultimately this will lead to an improved understanding of reaction mechanism and will enable the design of new reactions based on enzymatic molecular rearrangements. We adopt a multidisciplinary approach to studying enzymatic mechanisms using a combination of experiments with and

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² 'To be, or not to be: that is the question' (William Shakespeare, *Hamlet, Act III, Sc. 1*).

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without the enzyme. The former involves stereochemical [2] and spectroscopic studies [3] with pure enzymes. The latter entails chemical model studies [4], as well as theoretical investigations (*ab initio* molecular orbital calculations of reaction pathways) [5]. This paper will describe enzymatic investigations pertinent to the carbon skeleton mutases methylmalonyl-CoA mutase, 2-methyleneglutarate mutase and glutamate mutase.

Studies of enzyme mechanisms underpin medical science, and in this case there is direct relevance to the mode of action of a vitamin. Furthermore, the specific enzymes of this project are found in *Clostridia* sp., some members of which are implicated in human disease (e.g. *Clostridium tetani*). Hence, a better understanding of these enzymes may be utilised for the development of new therapies against pathogenic organisms. Additionally, understanding the mechanisms of enzymatic reactions in which radicals are intermediates could aid the design of new synthetic reactions of potential value to the fine chemicals and pharmaceutical industries.

The Enzymes: Methylmalonyl-CoA Mutase, Glutamate Mutase and 2-Methyleneglutarate Mutase

The carbon skeleton rearrangements catalysed by methylmalonyl-CoA mutase (Scheme 1), 2-methyleneglutarate mutase (Scheme 2) [5, 6] and glutamate mutase (Scheme 3) [6] belong to a group of more than 10 similar reactions mediated by coenzyme B₁₂-dependent enzymes [7, 8]. In humans, mammals and some anaerobic bacteria propionate is oxidised *via* the coenzyme B₁₂-dependent carbon skeleton rearrangement of (*R*)-methylmalonyl-CoA to succinyl-CoA catalysed by methylmalonyl-CoA mutase. 2-Methyleneglutarate and glutamate mutase are similar to some other highly topical enzymes, such as isocitrate lyase (implicated in tuberculosis [9]), glutamate receptors in the brain [10] and central nervous system [11], fumarate reductase [12] and fumarase [13], in that they bind dicarboxylic acids.

Scheme 1. Equilibration of (*R*)-methylmalonyl-CoA and succinyl-CoA catalysed by methylmalonyl-CoA mutase.

The reactions catalysed by the B₁₂-dependent mutases are exceptional with respect to both type and mechanism. Organic radicals are intermediates in these reactions, as indicated by the detection of EPR resonances from catalytically active systems [2]. The removal of a hydrogen atom from a substrate molecule always starts at a relatively inactive C-H bond, even at a methyl group attached to an *sp*³ centre. This circumstance is evident from an examination of all known coenzyme B₁₂-dependent enzymatic rearrangements. A 'minimal mechanism' has

the coenzyme as a carrier of a 5'-deoxyadenosyl radical, which is released by homolysis of the Co-C σ -bond in the presence of a substrate molecule SH (Scheme 4). Hydrogen abstraction from a substrate molecule by the 5'-deoxyadenosyl radical gives 5'-deoxyadenosine and a substrate radical $S^{\bullet}$, which rearranges to a product radical $P^{\bullet}$. Exchange of hydrogen between the methyl group of 5'-deoxyadenosine and the product radical $P^{\bullet}$ gives product PH and regenerates the 5'-deoxyadenosyl radical.

Scheme 2. Equilibration of 2-methyleneglutarate **1** with (*R*)-3-methylitaconate **2** catalyzed by coenzyme B₁₂-dependent 2-methyleneglutarate mutase from *Eubacterium barkeri*.

Scheme 3. Equilibration of glutamate **3** with (*2S,3S*)-3-methylaspartate **4** catalyzed by coenzyme B₁₂-dependent glutamate mutase from *Clostridium cochlearium*.

Scheme 4. 'Minimal mechanism' for coenzyme B₁₂-dependent enzymatic rearrangements (AdoCH₂-Cbl = adenosylcobalamin, AdoCH₂[•] = 5'-deoxyadenosyl radical, doCH₃ = 5'-deoxyadenosine, Cbl[•] = cob(II)alamin; SH = substrate, PH = product, S[•] = substrate-derived radical, P[•] = product-related radical).

A critical issue to resolve with respect to Scheme 4 is the nature of the rearrangement of the substrate-derived radical $S^{\bullet}$ to the product-related radical $P^{\bullet}$, in which a group (e.g. the glycyl moiety in Scheme 2) migrates from one carbon atom (C-3 of glutamate in Scheme 3) to an adjacent carbon atom (C-4 of the glutamate in Scheme 3). For the carbon skeleton mutases, the two extreme possibilities for the migration are shown in Scheme 5 as a 1,2-shift without the migrating group X ever being detached from C-1 and/or C-2 (addition-elimination mechanism: Scheme 5, path *a*), or as a fragmentation-recombination mechanism in which the migrating group is detached from C-1 before it starts bonding to C-2 (Scheme 5, path *b*) [14].

Scheme 5. Addition-elimination (path *a*) and fragmentation-recombination (path *b*) mechanisms applicable to methylmalonyl-CoA mutase ($X = \text{COSCoA}$) and 2-methyleneglutarate mutase [$X = \text{C}(\text{=CH}_2)\text{CO}_2\text{H}$]; for glutamate mutase only path *b* is permissible.

Scheme 6. Possible pathways for 2-methyleneglutarate mutase (path *a*, addition-elimination; path *b*, fragmentation-recombination).

For Scheme 5 path *b*, the fragmentation could give either an alkene + a radical as shown or an alkene radical cation + an anion. For those substrates that contain a π -bond suitably placed in the migrating group [e.g. methylmalonyl-CoA, $X = \text{C}(\text{=O})\text{SCoA}$; 2-methyleneglutarate, $X = \text{C}(\text{=CH}_2)\text{CO}_2\text{H}$], an addition-elimination mechanism, maintaining bonding of the migrating group to C-1 or C-2 at all times, is a plausible alternative. This pathway has recently been explored for methylmalonyl-CoA mutase using *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations [4], which showed the possibility of substantial rate acceleration through 'partial protonation' of the carbonyl oxygen of the COSCoA group. Similar calculations on the 2-methyleneglutarate mutase reaction showed that an addition-elimination pathway, *via* intermediates 3–5 (Scheme 6, path *a*), was energetically more favourable than fragmentation-recombination *via* acrylate 6 and the 2-acrylate radical 7 (Scheme 6, path *b*) [15]. However, the actual mechanism utilised by the enzyme may be determined by the available functional groups in the protein and their steric disposition. Hence, the enzyme may utilise a relatively high energy pathway for the rearrangement, provided its energy barrier does not exceed the energy barrier for the rate-limiting step of the reaction, which is probably the hydrogen abstraction from substrate or product.

Figure 1. Schematic of the active site portion of the crystal structure of glutamate mutase showing the 'arginine claw'.

For glutamate mutase, fragmentation-recombination *via* acrylate and the 2-glycynyl radical seems to be the only possibility and was recently supported by the X-ray analysis of the enzyme [16], EPR studies [3] and by trapping radiolabelled acrylate and glycine [17]. The crystal structure of glutamate mutase shows that the substrate analogue, (*S,S*)-tartrate, is bound tightly by, not two, but three arginine residues (R66, R149, R100), in an arrangement termed the 'arginine claw' (see Figures 1 and 2) [18]. Presumably, a critical function of the claw is to sequester the substrate in its correct conformation [3] for fragmentation and prevent unwanted side-reactions with protein functional groups. Whilst the importance in binding the substrate is clear, the effects that the arginine claw may have on the reaction path are not immediately apparent. It has been postulated [16] that R66 and R149 may be required to control the geometry and/or prevent the escape of reactive intermediate radicals in the proposed fragmentation-recombination mechanism.

It is known that the X-ray crystal structures of B₁₂-dependent enzymes show considerable structural homology, while not always displaying high sequence homology [16]. It is therefore expected that 2-methyleneglutarate mutase, with a very similar substrate, will have high structural homology at its active site with glutamate mutase and thus a similar arginine claw structure.

Research at Newcastle

Rationale

The essence of our investigations is to explore the extent to which the arginine claw in glutamate mutase, and possibly 2-methyleneglutarate mutase, controls the rearrangement of substrate to product radical. During the rearrangement of glutamate to 3-methylaspartate, the relative positions of the two carboxylate groups must necessarily change. We envisage that glutamate mutase utilises the arginine claw as a means of adjusting to this structural modification. Whilst one arginine (R100) anchors the C-5 carboxylate of glutamate (or C-4 carboxylate of 3-methylaspartate), the migrating glycynyl moiety moves between the other two arginines (R66 and R149). This enables the handover, as in a relay race, of the carboxylate of the glycynyl group from one

arginine to another. Dicarboxylate binding proteins, such as glutamate receptors that do not catalyse mutase activity, display only one or two arginine residues at the site of binding [9, 10]. Similarly, isocitrate lyase and fumarase catalyse movements where the alignment of fragments to form the product has, perhaps, a different degree of flexibility than for glutamate mutase or 2-methyleneglutarate mutase. Thus, such enzymes only have one or two arginine or lysine residues [8, 12] and this suggests that the claw arrangement may be critical for the extreme degree of control required over radical intermediates. It is also interesting that arginines, rather than, say, lysines, are utilised in the claw. This may be because arginine enables the positive charge of the guanidinium moiety to be 'smeared' over a relatively large area, in contrast to the situation that would prevail with point charges. Thus, an investigation into the significance and influence that multiple arginine residues may have on substrate binding and enzymatic catalysis is timely. We are pursuing this subject with a combination of synthetic models, computational modelling studies and kinetic investigations. In this paper, preliminary model studies are described.

Chemical Model Studies

Synthetic Receptors

Many research groups have synthesised receptors for dicarboxylates [19] and other ligands [20]. We are synthesising artificial receptors based on biphenyl and trityl and systems (*Figure 2*) containing amino and guanidine groups. To enable the influence of arginine to be compared with that of lysine, we are also preparing receptors incorporating amino groups in place of selected guanidines. Scaffolds based on biphenyls and trityls are attractive because of their synthetic accessibility. Furthermore, the trityl systems provide a simple opportunity to create enzyme-like cavities with well-understood conformational flexibility. The ability of the receptors to adjust their conformation in a subtle manner is seen as critical to the development of models possessing mutase-like activity. The biphenyls can be synthesised using the Suzuki reaction. The trityls are prepared by coupling substituted metallo-arenes with a functionalised benzophenone.

Figure 2. Scaffolds for dicarboxylate receptors (X, Y, Z are guanidine or amine moieties, e.g. $X = \text{CH}_2\text{NHC}(=\text{NH}_2^+)\text{NH}_2$; $R = \text{H}$ or a group controlling conformation or solubility).

In preliminary studies we have synthesised a diphenyl that is 2,3'-disubstituted with a guanidinium moiety **8** and a trityl alcohol that is 3,4',4''-trisubstituted with an aminomethyl group **9** [21].

Complexation Studies with Diacids

The dissociation constants (K_d) for complexes between the synthetic receptor **8** (cf. previous Section) and selected diacids dianions (succinic, glutaric, adipic) have been measured by an NMR method and by isothermal titration calorimetry. Values of K_d in the range 10^4 – 10^5 M^{-1} were obtained, showing that receptor **8** is an effective binder for dicarboxates structurally related to the substrates/products of the coenzyme B₁₂-dependent mutases. Future work will seek to achieve high levels of discrimination between homologous diacids.

Syntheses of Radical Precursors and Putative Products

Following the development of receptors that bind 3-methylaspartate/glutamate and 3-methylitaconate/2-methyleneglutarate with relatively low K_d , we will synthesise precursors for the putative intermediate radicals in the reactions catalysed by glutamate and 2-methyleneglutarate mutase, respectively. Giese [22] and Newcomb [23] have shown the value of certain ketones as precursors of radicals, which are generated selectively by photolysis (at 320 nm for e.g. ${}^t\text{BuCOR} \rightarrow \text{R}\cdot$).

10a, **11a**, X = CO^tBu; **10b**, **11b**, X = free electron

We have therefore synthesised derivatives of 3-methylitaconate/2-methyleneglutarate **10a** and **11a**, from which the corresponding radicals **10b** and **11b** can be released photochemically (for an example of a synthesis see Scheme 7).

Scheme 7. Example of a synthesis of a photolabile precursor **11a** of radical **11b**

Photolyses and Product Studies

Complexes will be formed from radical precursors **10a** and **11a** and receptors, and subjected to photolyses using a medium pressure Hg lamp. The receptor-radical complexes are potential 'molecular machines' that may enable

the control of otherwise synthetically inaccessible radical rearrangements. In preliminary studies, photolysis of **10a** diethyl ester in 2-propanol solvent gave diethyl 2-methyleneglutarate among other products.

Conclusions

The first steps have been achieved in the quest to develop functional models of coenzyme B₁₂-dependent carbon skeleton mutases. The role of the complex B₁₂ coenzyme in the enzymatic reactions is to provide the adenosyl radical as an initiator of a reaction pathway *via* protein-bound free radicals. The cobalt atom of the coenzyme masks this reactive adenosyl radical until the arrival of a substrate molecule initiates homolytic cleavage of the cobalt-carbon σ -bond of the coenzyme. Hence, 'to B₁₂ or not to B₁₂' in this context is not an issue. The coenzyme provides an essential, special mechanism for protecting the adenosyl radical, a highly reactive primary organic radical.

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